

TITLE

JOYSTICK: CO-CREATION WITH A GAMING COMMUNITY

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CREDITS

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AUDIENCE AND THE GAMING COMMUNITY
IN MALMÖ.

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Joystick: Co-creation With a Gaming Community

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Joystick is a concert format where Malmö Symphony Orchestra (MSO) performs computer-game music. The format, which started in 2006, is highly popular and well visited, drawing mostly male gamers between the ages of eighteen and forty. The Joystick project wanted to explore how the relationship between MSO and the gaming community could be deepened and broadened, for example, by reaching more women and a broader age span. More specifically, the project aimed at exploring what community engagement processes such deepened relations demand.

The research into how to broaden and deepen the engagement was done through a long-term collaborative design process that stretched over a year and a half. It involved MSO, the gaming community MEGA (previously called Terebi Gemu), Malmö University researchers and interaction design students. The process focused on:

- defining values and motivations driving the gaming community's engagement in Joystick;
- developing and running new media and communication formats for Joystick;
- developing and trying out what a satisfying and engaging holistic experience entails that includes activities before, during, and after the concert. With a 'holistic experience' we mean how the concert, the communication, the scenography, the graphical profile, and side events (seminars, competitions etc.) work together and strengthen each other.

This report describes what was developed and insights gained from implementing them into the Joystick 6.0 concert.

Background and results from observations

Gamers' values and motivations of being involved in Joystick

Workshop at the MEGA premises with gamers, MSO, and university researchers.

Literature on audience engagement stresses the importance of getting to know the social and cultural values and motivational factors when building relationships with new communities or groups of people. Many cultural institutions that conduct surveys find out only what attending audiences think, and are therefore of little use when building new relationships. Furthermore, surveys are not mutual learning opportunities. The collaborative design process, which the design decisions were based on, pointed out central values and motivational factors pertaining to the gaming community, which were that:

- gamers see engagement as active participation, as gaming is an active cultural expression;
- they view gaming as a serious art form on par with classical music and that it should be respected as such;
- the communication should happen over a long time, and it should be transparent and adjusted to their way of expressing themselves and

communicating; that is, less formal and pitch-perfect and instead more bi-directional and frequent;

- gamers want a consistent holistic experience – a “folk” festival experience rather than a formal concert;
- the collaboration needs to start early, else their input simply becomes a badly organized add-on resulting in a suboptimal outcome;
- the members of the gaming community are willing to share their knowledge, as well as become Joystick ambassadors connecting MSO to other gaming communities if MSO is mutually engaged.

The Joystick blog and social media

The image shows a screenshot of a blog post on the Joystick website. The header features the Joystick logo, which includes a violin and a joystick, and navigation links for 'RETROLOPPIS' and 'DAGENS SPELMELODI'. The main content area displays a photograph of two young men, Maren Reck and Jordan Scapinello, standing next to a double bass. Below the photo is the article title 'Bonusonsdag: Från två världar – en intervju om två perspektiv på spel och dess musik', the author 'Alexander', the date '26 March 2014', and tags 'Slider, Uncategorized'. The article text discusses the players' backgrounds and their perspectives on game music. On the right side, there is a sidebar with social media icons for Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, RSS, and YouTube, a 'PRENUMERERA' (Subscribe) section with an email input field and a 'Ja tack!' button, and a 'BOKA KONCERTBILJETTER' (Book concert tickets) section with a promotional image for the Malmö Symphony Orchestra.

A post on the Joystick blog: An interview with two double-bass players who have quite different opinions about game music.

The community engagement consisted of using social media platforms such as a dedicated blog (joystick.mso.se), Twitter, Instagram, Flickr, YouTube, and Facebook. The communication on these platforms ran between January 23 and May 10, 2014. The blog grew out of the Joystick Challenge blog, which was created to communicate the results from the workshops with MEGA that ran during the fall of 2013 and in January 2014. As such the blog can be said to have run between

September 9, 2013, and May 10, 2014. The official public launch of the blog was done at the Winter-een-mas event at Spelens Hus, Malmö. The event, which was broadcast live through a Twitch channel, besides consisting of various game competitions, also consisted of a Skype interview with the Joystick producer and concert host Orvar Säfström.

The central purpose of the blog, which was run by the gamer and game blogger Alexander Cederholm (Alex) in dialogue with MSO and university researchers, were:

- to establish an online community where enthusiasts of computer-game music can gather to read as well as share and spread their knowledge and passion for computer-game music;
- to *communicate* rather than *inform* the audience about computer-game music at large, but with a focus on building up a momentum to the Joystick 6.0 concert, thus expanding the concert experience in time;
- to give the audience better insight into what happens ‘behind the scenes’;
- to engage the gamers in influencing part of the set list, the scenography, and side events;
- to acknowledge that computer-game music is a serious art form where Malmö Symphony orchestra can ‘take the lead’ and have an editorial role;
- that the concert should be connected to and be arranged at the same time as computer-game events are held in the city.

The blog consisted of posts that were divided into the following themes: ‘Today’s Song’ that discussed computer-game music; ‘Behind the Scenes’ comprised of interviews with musicians, the conductor, the host, and the producers of Joystick; and ‘The Voting for Music’ to be played during Act 1. Two posts on average were published per week, but intensified in frequency as the concert dates approached.

The purpose of the blog, as Alex stressed in one of his first posts¹, was not only to market the concert, but to gather people interested in sharing memories of game music and discussing broadly, both old and new, computer-game music. The tone of the blog was purposely colloquial, frequent, and dialogical – in contrast, for example, to a printed program that is carefully written and designed. An advantage

¹ <http://joystick.mso.se/2014/01/vem-jag-ar-och-vad-jag-vill/>

with blogs is, as is well known, that the content can be altered and corrected, that it can be published with short notice, and that it is searchable and ‘spreadable’. That said, the two most important aspects of the Joystick blog was that it was written in a manner that is frequently found within the gaming communities and that it opened up for transparent dialogue with its followers.

The level of engagement from the followers of the blog turned out to be high. What engaged the ‘readers’ the most was suggesting and voting for songs to be included in the first act of the concert, which was dedicated to retro game music. At times, the song suggestions were followed by long texts motivating why a particular song should be included.

**MAIL FRÅN:
ORVAR**

En uppdatering angående era önskelåtar inför Joystick 6.0

 Önskelåtar

För en tid sedan bad vi er önska musik till den första akten på JOYSTICK 6.0. Musiken skulle komma från spel före 1995 (akt 2 innehåller bara spelmusik efter 2010). Det gällde också att tänka lite musikaliskt, och gärna komma med tankar om orkestrering och annat – och vi har fått in massor av intressanta förslag!

Vi kommer snart att presentera de låtar som ni ska få rösta om, men innan dess några ord om de låtar vi sorterat bort.

Här är några exempel på önskningar som kommit in, men som inte stämmer med våra kriterier vad gäller releaseår:

The producer and concert host, Orvar Säfström, communicating with the blog readers.

The blogger and the Joystick producers had different opinions on how transparent the processes of requesting and voting for songs should be. Shortly after the request period ended, the blog editor published two posts that gave examples of what songs the blog readers had requested, along with the longer texts motivating why a particular song had been requested.² These two posts were ‘shared’ many times by the blog followers in other social media channels. It was a type of content that acknowledged the competence of the gamers and put individual readers in the spotlight; it was content ‘made’ by the readers, and they were willing to share it. However, the concert producers wanted this activity to stop. First, they didn’t want ‘a list of song requests’ to be public since they wanted to be able to add songs that had not been requested because they wanted to give the impression that Act 1 was completely based on the gamers’ request and assumed that if it was made visible it would upset them. Second, they didn’t want individual songs requests to be published in the case that these songs were not included in the medleys/suites that were later to be voted upon. During the voting process, the producers asked not to disclose the number of people who voted. After the voting ended, the number of votes for each voting item was only described in percent in relation to the other voting items, not the number of votes.

The blogger’s and the producers’ view on how transparent the voting should be revealed differences in opinion how to work with audiences. The blogger wanted the process to be as transparent as possible, while the producers wanted it to be less transparent. The blogger was foremost focused on the values and wishes of the audience, which dictated what he would publish. The producers, on the other hand, wanted to be in control and worried about that the audience would choose ‘wrong’ songs – for example, songs that are hard to get the rights to or difficult to make scores to; songs that could not be included and therefore would disappoint the audience. Also, they did not want to disclose to the audience that they themselves added songs to the voting list, as they assumed that this would not be favorably looked upon by the audience.

The statistics from various social media channel show that the communication strategy was quite successful in reaching out to the audience. The

² <http://joystick.mso.se/2014/02/detta-ar-musiken-ni-vill-hora-under-joystick-6-0-del-01/> and <http://joystick.mso.se/2014/02/detta-ar-musiken-ni-vill-hora-under-joystick-6-0-volym-02/>

number of page views on MSO webpages (including mso.se and joystick.mso.se) related to the Joystick concert was significantly higher in 2014 compared to 2013. During the period ‘three months before the concert’ to ‘a week before the concert’, the total number of page views was between two and five times higher. The number of page views during the concert week was about three times higher in 2014 compared to 2013, peaking at about 5000 page views on the concert days. The number of page views, however, says nothing about how many individuals viewed Joystick related webpages. The data, for various reasons, is hard to interpret and compare with the 2013 concert. That said, it is reasonable to conclude that the number of people exposed online to the concert was significantly higher in 2014.

The hashtag #joystick6 became well established during 2014 as a result of the social media strategy. A Joystick hashtag existed already in 2013, but it was used significantly less by the audience and it was not used or promoted by MSO. On Instagram, 64 photos by 44 persons were uploaded. (This excludes photos uploaded by MSO and Malmö University researchers). Most of the photos published were from the days of the concerts. They primarily depicted the concert hall, purchases made, pixel-art sprites, and selfies. Almost no pictures were taken of pins the visitors made, game stations, or the computer-games art put on display in the foyer. The profile @gaytenor, run by the social media active and gay rights advocate opera tenor Rickard Söderberg who sang at the concert, had the greatest impact.

Rickard Söderberg, tenor soloist at the Joystick concert, shared many photos related to the concert on Instagram.

Similarly, on Twitter, the #joystick6 hashtag became well established and had around 50 twitterers that made around 100 tweets during the concert days. On YouTube the most watched Joystick-related clips were the interviews with Sabina Zweiacker and Rickard Söderberg who both had 500 views shortly after the concerts. The video with the conductor Charles Hazelwood received 200 views. Fewer bootleg video recordings were spread compared to the previous concerts. The most popular webpages related to the Joystick concert, based on the number of 'shares' on Facebook³, were as follows:

Shares	Media
173	The program page (x2) from the Joystick blog.
154	The Joystick 6.0 program on mso.se.
132	The post "Open Pixel Night & Pixel Perfect Windows" from the Joystick blog.
107	The YouTube video made by the Joystick team with the soprano Sabina.
104	The YouTube video made by the Joystick team with tenor Rickard Söderberg.
90	The index page, joystick.mso.se.
84	"What music do you want to hear during act 1?", from the Joystick blog.
71	The program in English, from the Joystick blog.
65	"The Flea market" post from the Joystick blog.
53	"Pixel music fills the concert hall", from the newspaper Sydsvenskan (May 9, 2014).
45	"What music do you want to hear at Joystick 6.0?", from the Joystick blog.
42	"This is the music we want to hear, part 1 & 2", from the Joystick blog.
28	Vox Pop - "this is what the audience had to say about the Joystick concert", from the Joystick blog.
23	YouTube video of the Final Fantasy VI rehearsal
22	The voting results of what pieces should be played during act 1 from the Joystick blog.
12	The interview with the host Orvar Säfström in newspaper Sydsvenskan titled "Computer-game music has a huge audience" ("Spelmusiken har en enorm publik" (Sydsvenskan May 9, 2014).
12	"An interview with the Joystick producer Magnus Johansson", from the Joystick blog.
9	The YouTube-video with the conductor Charles Hazelwood.

³ The number of 'shares' on Facebook can be seen by adding a URL after the '=' sign: <http://graph.facebook.com/?id=>

A screenshot from a YouTube video with the soprano Sabina Zweigacker.

The data shows, first of all, that the Joystick blog in interaction with Facebook sharing is a more important media channel and has a greater impact than *Sydsvenskan*, the largest Swedish newspaper in southern Sweden, when it comes to sharing articles and posts. The most appreciated articles/posts concern the program (what will be played), posts that have to do with participative activities related to the concert (the pixel-art scenography and the voting of the set list for Act 1 of the concert), as well as the interviews with the soloists Sabina Zweigacker and Rickard Söderberg. The audience thus premieres beloved star musicians more than the host, the producers, and the conductor, who are spread considerably less through social media channels. Interestingly, the number of people who shared the post that the voting had started was greater than the number of people who shared the voting results. The number of people posting tweets and Instagram photos may at first seem meager, only around fifty people. However, fifty twitterers and instagramers is a significant number, as most people on social media channels mostly read and at times spread what others have posted. These fifty publishers can be viewed as important MSO ambassadors.

Co-creative scenography and side events

A hi-res rendition of Majora's Mask made with sticky notes by an avid gamer.

During the workshops it was stressed that the surrounding events and the scenography should complement and give a holistic experience to the concert experience. The visual look in the concert hall, the foyer, and on the digital platforms should have a clear and consistent look. Along the same line, the events should have a clear connection to the Joystick 6.0 set list, which was retro computer-game music and modern classics. Given that the set list was divided into two quite distinct themes – that in turn have distinct visual expressions – it was decided to focus on retro computer music. The reason for this decision was that MEGA has a tradition of reinterpreting and remediating the pixel aesthetics of early computer games, for example by making the first level of the Super Mario Bros game with fusible beads.

Fusible-bead art shown by a gamer at MEGA's premises during one of the workshops.

Given the size of the concert hall and the foyer, working with fusible beads was not an option. It was thus early on decided to work with colored sticky notes. MEGA members in collaboration with the set designer Eva Wendelboe Kuczynski and the interaction designer Marie Ehrndal did the detailing of the so-called pixel scenography concept.

The team decided that the do-it-yourself pixel concept should be interactive and have simple game elements, but not staged as a competition but rather a social, collaborative engagement similar in spirit to social events arranged by MEGA. The ambition was that part of the scenography should be built before the concert and part of it during the concert. Beside the participative nature of the set design, the aim and purpose of the scenography was to signal – both inside and outside the concert hall – how the symphony orchestra and the 8-bit videogame culture fused together through a temporary transformation of the concert hall.

An open call⁴ was sent to gamers and visual artists through various social media channels and other networks, in which they were invited to make pixel art on the concert hall windows that would be visible from the street and in the foyer.

⁴ <http://joystick.mso.se/2014/04/var-med-och-skapa-pixelperfekta-fonster-pa-konserthuset/>

Although the windows were the primary ‘canvas’, the pixel art branched onto the floor, and the ladies and men’s room were also filled with sticky notes and pens where the audience could make ‘toilet graffiti’. The participants were also offered that their making of a pixel artwork could be stop-motion recorded, which several participants accepted and that they shared through social media.

Four days before the concert, the concert hall was opened up to pixel ‘artists’ who had signed up for the event and submitted pixel motives – called sprites in the gaming world – which they wanted to make. The aim was to get twenty people to sign up, but we ended up with ten people who signed up. A public pixel night⁵, the evening before the concert, was also arranged. On the day of the concert, the concert hall was opened at 3 PM so that the audience could come and make and look at the pixel art. All fifty-two windows on the concert hall’s first and second floors ended up being filled with motives. The motives ranged from complex 16-bit pixel motives that took several days to make, to simple Pacman motives made by families waiting for the concert to start.

⁵ <http://joystick.mso.se/2014/05/open-pixel-night/>

Pixel artists at work in the concert hall foyer.

The pixel-art concept resulted in a dynamic scenography that slowly grew into existence before and during the concerts. This was a scenography created by the audience expressing their passionate engagement with computer games. The scenography was thus created through the involvement of many concertgoers, which contributed to that they felt it was ‘their’ concert hall and that they were part of a larger community. It also clearly signaled that computer games is an art form like any other and not an individual experience inside a computer game. It as well drew and engaged couples that wanted to make a creation together and partners soon to be married that booked ten windows to decorate – as their eve-of-wedding party ritual – to honor the bridegroom’s fascination of graphical motives.

Producing a set-design concept built around audience engagement needs to be arranged differently than a traditional set design. It demands that the production team is comfortable with the uncertainties that handing over some of the ownership to the audience entails. The set-design team also needs to have the skill to engage and facilitate other people’s creative engagement. It also demands that the team can connect to people interested and that the invitation is made in the right way. The co-creative framework likewise needs to be framed so that they find it inspiring and challenging. The last two parameters were in place as the design team worked closely with MEGA and because of the gamer-run blog with strong connections to gaming communities.

In sum the pixel-art concept showed that:

- a simple DIY set-design format can grow into an immersive, creative event and a visual expression that increases the audience's sense of belonging and 'ownership' in the sense that the concert hall becomes theirs if the right conditions for engagement are created;
- the pixel art making, which ran over several days, drew positive attention to the concert both online and offline as the decoration of the hall progressed as people passed by the hall and the participants shared photos of their pixel art in-the-making on social platforms. Similarly, during the concerts the pixel art was seen as photo opportunities and it was extensively used as visual backdrop for photos shared on social media platforms;
- the communication about participating in the production needs to be precise and the communication channels need to be in place. In this regard, it was essential to engage ambassadors with clear roles and responsibilities to work on the project;
- the cultural institution needs to be willing to let go of having complete control and a pre-given structure for how the process is to evolve;
- working with co-creative community-based set design demands specific design competences, namely knowing how to create co-creative formats and how to 'recruit' and be in dialogue with external participants. These competences need to be recruited if they are not part of institution;
- it is demanding to create a new visual expression and a new practice and culture of producing an event and a set design within a cultural institution. It demands constant dialogue with internal and external partners on how to run the process and what the outcome will be.

Pixel Art decorating the concert hall foyer at the Joystick concert.

Audience survey results

The evaluation of the Joystick experiment and the concert was done through observations, face-to-face discussions, and through online and printed surveys. On May 27, 2014, about two weeks after the concert, the online survey was sent to 657 email addresses, and 118 (18 percent) responses had been given on June 4, 2014. The survey consisted of the following questions: In whose company did you attend the concert? What did you do before the concert? How familiar are you with the Joystick blog? When did you buy your ticket? How did you find out about the concert? What made you want to go to the concert? What did you think of the concert? What did you do beside listen to the concert? Have you been to an MSO concert before? Are you engaged in a gaming organization? What did you do after the concert? Would you be interested in other MSO concerts? What would be the ultimate concert format according to you? Would you like to learn more about classical music? Additional thoughts?

Survey demographics

Of those that answered the survey, 61 percent of the respondents were in the span 24-38 years of age. 21 percent of the answers were from people 45 years of age or older. We expected the age group 18-23 to be the biggest. However, this age span only made up 9 percent of those answering the survey. The 45+ age group was thus more than twice as large as the youngest age group, amounting to about one fifth of the total answers. The 45+ attended the concert with friends and partners, and not predominantly with their children, as perhaps one easily could presuppose. Less than half of the respondents answered that they attended the concert with a relative. This is in line with the other age groups who predominantly went to the concerts with friends and secondly with a partner. Very few concertgoers came alone. A concert is thus, not surprisingly, a social activity that you want to experience and share with others and preferably with a friend with shared interests. Only one of the respondents were younger than eighteen years old, which can be explained by the fact that you need to be eighteen to buy tickets and the survey only went out to ticket buyers. The age groups were quite mixed, but generally older than what was expected. That the average age was higher than expected can be explained by the fact that we still perceive computer games as

being primarily a youth culture and we forget that it has been around for almost forty years. However, the low number of 18-24 year-olds can partly be explained by a badly communicated discount campaign. Possibly it can also be explained by the fact that retro-game music is more attractive to the older generation of gamers.

The audience was predominantly male and this is mirrored in the survey where 75 percent of the respondents were male. This can be contrasted with the fact that 50 percent of gamers are women. Given that no previous survey exists, it is difficult to assess accurately if more women attended Joystick 6.0 than previous year's concerts, but the impression from the MEGA gamers, MSO, and the researchers was that that considerably more women attended Joystick 6.0.

10 percent answered that they had game-related work or studies, but not within the game industry. 37 percent answered that they are or had been engaged in a gaming organization.

Almost half of the respondents purchased their tickets during the four weeks prior to the concert, whereof one-fifth of the tickets were purchased one week before the concert. The other half purchased tickets 1-6 months before the concert. 21 percent learned about the concert through friends, acquaintances, or relatives, while 13 percent found out about the concert through flyers and posters. The more than 60 percent who answered "other" said "e-mail, the MSO website, the Joystick blog, Facebook, and the MSO season program".

95 percent of the respondents had previously attended Joystick concerts or other MSO concerts. Only 1 respondent says that this was his/her first concert with MSO. The program did not play a decisive role on when they bought tickets. The program was released quite late, which may have affected the role the program had when people were deciding whether to purchase tickets or not. However, it may also indicate that the audience is 'sold on' and supportive of the format, and that the specifics of each concert is not a decisive factor when buying tickets. This does not mean that the program is unimportant. On the contrary, the program is highly important, as the many discussions attest that the MEGA gamers had where they compared and ranked the various Joystick concerts.

The most common Joystick concertgoer is thus a man between 29-34 years of age. He has a job that is not game related, he has never been engaged in a gaming organization, and he attends the concert with his friends. He buys concert tickets between one and three months before the concert and is a returning visitor. This

representation, building on the most common features, is only telling to some degree. It is far from the diverse mix that makes up the Joystick audience. Chiseling out the ‘standard’ visitor is useful primarily to get a picture of what is in the margins and where a ‘growth’ potential is, or where at least the most democratic potential is situated if diversity is the guiding light when listing guidelines for reaching more diverse audiences.

Before-the-concert activities

Half of the respondents stated that they did nothing in particular before the concert. However, many of them participated in the foyer activities. (In the survey, ‘prior to the concert’ is interpreted as that which happens outside the concert hall).

“The whole family met at a restaurant and then went to the concert hall some time before the concert to look at the activities in the foyer.”

“I was at home fixing my hair and listened to the music that would be played at the concert so that I would be able to tell them apart.”

“I made a few sticky-note figures and helped others to make sticky-note motives. I also made some bargains at the flea market and ate at a restaurant.”

“Went to the pub and met my colleagues.”

“Went to a home party at a friends home together with a group of friends going to the concert.”

“We spent two hours prior to the concert at the concert hall on Joystick related activities.”

“We listened to other game music (and we became sad because we could not find any old Joystick recordings). We went to a pub. We looked around at the activities offered at the concert hall before the concert.”

About 40 percent participated in social activities together with acquaintances, friends, or family prior to the concert where the most frequent activity, not surprisingly, was eating out, as the above quotes attest to. Recurrent activities were also listening to computer-game music or meeting up at a friend’s home to get into the mood. Few respondents stated that they engaged in ‘educational’ activities.

The concert

Joystick 6.0 was generally well received and the audience cherished the vocal pieces. Many respondents also appreciated the retro theme, which was considered 'spot-on'. The number of positive reactions that the retro theme received shows that the audience experienced that they had been heard, as some of them had participated in suggesting and voting on parts of the program.

"Excellent, both the old part with the Nintendo medley and the new one with Assassin's 'Black Flag' and the opera duo!"

"Awesome! Especially the Amiga- and Nintendo medleys as well as 'The Last of Us.'"

"Fantastic, beautiful music and a fantastic medley. I really liked that 'Mega Man' was part of the repertoire and that in fact the audience's opinion was listened to, which was evident in the three medleys performed."

"It was a lot better than last year. It had a much better mix of old and new than last year. I must confess that modern game music is not as interesting to listen to as the old-school music."

"I loved that there was a lot of retro. I have missed that the last two years. More retro to the people!"

"The retro part was fantastic and ambitious!"

The above reactions, as earlier stated, show that audience felt that MSO had listened to their wishes and that they think that the concerts are of high quality and relevant, which in turn leads to the audience having a high level of trust towards MSO. It was at the same time clear that some concertgoers did not have any relationship to retro computer-game music. For them the second half of the concert was considerably more attractive.

After the concert

Many visitors spent considerable time in the foyer after the concert. MSO had, however, not made any plans to accommodate the audience's wish and need to linger after the concert in the concert hall. The foyer was quiet and the activities disassembled, the bistro was closed and after a while the lights were turned off signaling that the audience should leave. Orvar (one of the Joystick producers and the concert host) and some musicians, however, went out into the foyer to meet

the audience, which was well received. Many concertgoers needed, as the below quotes show, to ‘digest’ the concert experience by talking to others about it, by listening to music, or by playing computer games.

“Digested the experience.”

“Evaluated the experience with my friends on our way home.”

“Took a walk and talked about the concert and had some ice cream.”

“Checked if I could by a recording of the concert and went to a friend’s home party.”

“Ate and discussed the set list and games in general.”

“Visited a restaurant close to the venue and then went back to the hotel to watch the final moments of Eurovision Song Contest from Copenhagen.”

“We walked around in the concert hall, but everything was closed so we took a taxi home :/”

“Went home and played Diablo 3.”

“I bicycled home and did not listen to any music. Why? To better remember how the concert sounded.”

“My son and I went home. We talked a lot about the concert and previous ones that we have attended.”

“After the concert we stood outside and talked about it and then we went home.”

“Went and took a beer with my daughter.”

Many of the respondents of the survey thus stated that they needed time to digest the experience and talk to others about it. After the concert, many of them went to a restaurant or pub to eat or have drinks together with friends or close others where the concert experience would be an important topic of discussion. Another common activity, amongst game enthusiasts not the least, was to go home to play computer games.

Several respondents stated that they felt inspired, that the concert increased the appetite for computer games and music, and that they wished to prolong the experience.

“We went to a fantastic hamburger joint and thereafter my brother went to Lund, and two of my friends and I went back to Kristianstad and played

PlayStation over LAN all weekend long.”

“Bought some candy and went to Åhus and played games half/the whole night.”

“I was elated and euphoric. I suddenly had an urge to play Skyrim and Final Fantasy 6 at the same time, but failed to practically combine the two games.”

“We went home and watched videos from the last concert and played ‘nostalgic games’.”

The Joystick blog

About two-thirds of the respondents wrote that they knew about the Joystick blog and one-fifth stated that they frequently read it.

”Today’s Melody and the short, but interesting interviews...most of it.”

”Different things, Today’s Melody, the voting on what retro songs [in the] medley should be played at the concert, the info on pixel art and the retro-game flea market and the concert program.”

”I read quite a bit of the ‘Today’s game music melody’ that I found really interesting and well written.”

”Today’s melody, tips on melodies that will be performed at the concert. I read about the competitions and voting. I have also read what Alexander wrote about for example game music that was not performed during the concert. I read about different events that have been arranged.”

”Interviews with members of the orchestra, the conductor, vocalists and today’s game melody. I read about it after last years concert.”

”Game music interviews, information about the event. I listened to clips and read a little bit about the background to the Mario suite and about the retro flea market.”

”The voting above all. Skimmed ‘today’s melody’.”

”[I read] most of it and listened to several of the tips on game music. Interviews, today’s melody, the launch of the blog.”

”Today’s melody, interviews with different people working in or with the orchestra. Good work with the blog!”

”The blog is much appreciated!”

”It would be nice if the blog would return in the future.”

The blog was highly appreciated and did not receive any negative critique at all and, as the last quote shows, that it should continue. The statements above also show that both ‘Today’s Melody’ and the interviews with the musicians are particularly appreciated. One quote foregrounds the value of the voting, which was, as was discussed earlier, shared extensively in social media.

Future Development

Many of the Joystick 6.0 concertgoers had attended other MSO concerts. More than half of the respondents had attended a concert where MSO played their ordinary repertoire. 94 percent stated that they would like to attend other concerts with MSO. 41 percent answered that they would like to learn more about classical music. The majority of the respondents, however, were unsure if they would like to learn more.

The audience is highly engaged and do not lack suggestions on other concert formats that could be offered. A majority of them mentioned themes from television drama series and film music as particularly interesting formats. Also, many suggested that a more mixed and experimental format where classical music and various pop-cultural expressions met would be interesting.

“I would like to see a mix of game and film music, as they are closely related.”

“Film music and game music together in a awesome combination! I have always had a weakness for ELO that mixes classical music and rock. I would want to experience a concert that mixes symphonic music and electronic music.”

“Interactive concerts are always fun. It would have some sort of talk between the pieces where the musicians talk about a piece or on a more general level talk about how it is to play in an orchestra and how different it is to play Joystick.”

“Independent of a particular composer aim for classical pieces that are close to film music (The Hall of the Mountain King etc). Also, interpretations of modern pieces with a mixture of modern instruments (see for example Apocalyptika from Finland).”

“I would like a cool mix of different things and genres that somehow meet. Film and games are not that far from each other and it would be fantastic to find some sort of common denominator to make some sort of crossover concert.

“I have been to film-music concerts with MSO and there are too few of that kind. Holst’s ‘The Planets’ should be played again. More science-fiction

concerts with music from *Oblivion*, *Independence Day*, the television series *Fringe*, *Star Trek*, or concerts with themes such as Han Zimmer, Trevor Rabin, John Williams, etc.”

“Game music, alternative film music with large video projections.”

Many respondents specifically mentioned that they appreciated meeting the musicians, and many also expressed an interest in more direct interaction and audience participation.

“We went and talked to the incredibly competent soprano and told her that we gladly would want to see her again next year.”

“In-your-face music! Sit close to the musicians.”

Many of the respondents showed an interest in learning more about classical music at large. Many of them also suggested how the music could be made more accessible, understandable, and interesting to the audience.

“An educational concert where the maestro talks and explains the history, music techniques, and variations. Let us get closer to the music and become more than just an audience, teach us something.”

“Classical music on the theme ‘Time’: Big Bang to the Apocalypse, or on Love: agape/erotic, or Space: Micro-cosmos, the Higgs particle, and Dark Matter; or a Dance theme: From a minuet to street dance, or on the theme on the environment: Nature/industry, or on the theme ‘global’: Music from different cultures. All with cool lighting and scenography and with a conductor that is filmed so that the audience can see him/her from the front as well as a camera that can zoom in on the musicians.”

“That the musicians interact with, for example, something that happens on a screen behind the orchestra.”

“Classical science-fiction film music would be epic to see performed live. Film music would be bigwig. If for example Ennio Morricone’s soundtrack to ‘The Good, The Bad and The Ugly’ would be performed then not only I, but also all of my friends would be forced to go to that concert. Or, Hans Zimmer’s ‘Face/Off’ soundtrack would be pompous.”

“Film music from blockbusters, like ‘Lord of the Rings’ played by MSO. If you choose easily recognized music, and preferably within fantasy and sci-fi, it is impossible to fail.”

“A fantastic concert could consist of a style study that starts with a classical piece that then floats towards famous pieces from film music, game music, which in turn floats to impressionistic classical pieces that again to impressionistic film music and from there to game music in the same style – guided by a competent host that explains the relationships.”

“The Ultimate concert No. 1: MSO plays together with a hard rock band, alternatively that MSO plays hard rock songs in a classical manner. The ultimate concert No. 2: An instrumental evening with heavy and dark music: Grieg’s ‘Hall of The Mountain King,’ Wagner’s ‘Ride of The Valkyries’ mixed with classical monster songs from the film world. A concert with not so strict borders, I listen just as well to a classical cello piece by Bach as computer-game music, film music, and progressive metal. Why just stick to one kind of music? Than you never will get the devoted to develop a taste for other music styles. My dream concert could have film music from ‘Pride and Prejudice’ and Cinema Paradiso, interpretations of music by the progressive rock band Dream Theater, interpretations of George Harrison songs, music from Japanese bullet head games (which you have had, but Dementori has really nice music), jazzy autumn leafs, what a wonderful world, and Segovia guitar and ballet music from Spartacus. Why not ‘Amazing Grace’ on bagpipes as well? I am 100 percent serious. I love to go to a ‘RANDOM’ concert here where the audience was as mixed as at a Joystick concert.”

Conclusion

The collaborative exploration of how MSO could deepen and broaden their engagement with the Joystick audience showed that a long-term mutual learning process is productive for both MSO and the gaming community. It was essential to take the time to learn about gamers’ values and motivations for attending and co-arranging Joystick concerts; values and motivations that subsequent design decisions were clearly grounded in and informed by, rather than mere guessing and stereotypical understanding of the audience. Although the Joystick design process led to a deepened engagement, it was less successful in broadening the audience base, even though it was generally agreed that the number of women visitors increased.

The Joystick blog and other social media activities led to a significant increase in engagement during the weeks before the concert, which loaded the concertgoers with anticipation and excitement. Devoted Joystick fans were willing to share their knowledge about game music as well as share their contacts so that more people would know about the concert. Some of the blog’s significant communicative features were that the communication was transparent and adjusted to the audience members’ ways of communicating and expressing themselves. It was less formal and pitch-perfect and instead more bi-directional and frequent. It also showed that the gamers and the producers disagreed on how transparent the communication should be.

The experiment also showed that a holistic approach to media is needed. Close attention needs to be paid to how mediated relationship building connects to face-to-face activities happening in the foyer, at workshops, in other venues, or out in the city. It also means that the aesthetics of the media expression need to be tightly connected to the music performed and be consistent across media platforms: Print, web, foyer, and the concert hall. The DIY collaborative set design led to an increased sense of belonging and ownership of the concert, as well as it drew positive attention and was seen as photogenic backdrops, which was highly 'spreadable' through social media. An interactive set design however, demands, that well functioning communication channels with the audience are up and running, and a constant internal and external dialogue. It also demands that the cultural institution is willing to let go of the control and allow for more open-ended processes.

The audience was predominantly male and this is mirrored in the survey where 75 percent of the respondents were male. Many of the concertgoers engaged in social activities before and after the concert and expressed a wish to be able to stay longer in the concert hall. Joystick 6.0 was generally well received and the audience cherished the vocal pieces. The respondents considered MSO to have significant knowledge on gaming music and they trusted their professionalism. Many of the respondents showed an interest in learning more about classical music at large. Many respondents also happily shared ideas about new concert formats that MSO could develop.

Discussion

The open-ended collaborative explorations led to informed experiments in the midst of ongoing production. We had from the start a general framework, but did not know the specifics of what we would end up producing. The productions came about through constant weaving and negotiations where the different partners listened to each other's values, needs, know-how, and organizational constraints and possibilities. The results have significantly deepened the relationship between MSO and gamers. The process of getting to know each other's values and motivations, possibilities, and constraints is, however, time-consuming. Arranging the collaboration in an open-ended mutual learning was essential, as it meant that the gaming community and MSO negotiated how to work together, rather than that

the partners subsumed to tightly predefined constraints.

When developing new ways of working together, a new practice is developed; in this case, a new practice on how the Joystick concert could be collaboratively planned and communicated. The partners worked together over long period of time and started to plan the concert well in advance, rather than only a few weeks before the concert. This led to that the concert and its surrounding activities could be developed thoroughly, leading to a consistent, holistic experience instead of quickly put together add-on activities. It also allowed the gamers to influence, to a larger extent than previous years, part of the program, the aesthetical expression, and the surrounding activities. This trust, given to them by MSO, in turn led to a higher commitment from the gamers to engage in ambassadorship and in the planning.

The collaborative planning of the concert went largely well. The partners could agree on setting up a blog (that would be run by a gamer) several months before the concert, on engaging gamers in making pixel art in the concert hall foyer, and on the foyer activities. The biggest disagreement concerned the voting on what music should be included in Act 1 of the concert. Partly this depended on that the concert program is a more essential issue than how to communicate about the concert, the concert's aesthetical expression, and the foyer activities. It also partly depended on that the producers of Joystick and the gamers had different views on how transparent the voting process should be, where the producers wished to make their influence on Act 1 less apparent. The gamers on the other hand had no problem with the producers also deciding on the program. The gamers, however, wanted the voting process to be as transparent as possible, as that is more just. A non-transparent voting process, although looking more like the gamers decided, was seen as less 'democratic' and just, as it feigned the actual power given to the gamers. It should also be noted that given the increased number of partners it increased the organizational complexity and demanded increased communication.

The participatory communication and co-creation strategy, which included the blog and other social media channels and face-to-face activities in the foyer, led to greater engagement, different understandings of computer game music, and the gradual building up of expectations. MSO was open to adjusting their ways of communicating and graphic expression to the gamers' way of communicating and

aesthetics. The tone was, for example, less formal and more dialogical, and the blog was updated frequently. That said, with Joystick we aimed to create a balance between MSO's visual profile and gaming aesthetics. To what degree a cultural institution is able to target their communication and visual expression to different groups demands that the institution has in-house competence that can communicate in different ways or that the institution works with external partners. It also demands finding ways so that the main form of communication and the main visual expression can work together with targeted ways of communicating and visual expressions, else the institution risks appearing to its audience as fragmented.

Opening up for co-creative set-design activities, such as making pixel art in the foyer, worked well with the target group. It demands, however, a set designer that knows how to work with co-creation and open-ended processes. It also demands that the institution has already good connections and communications channels. A large number of highly committed participants are not to be expected, as it time-consuming. However, as the Joystick production showed, a few highly dedicated gamers – along with providing less demanding forms of participation – worked well together and was immensely appreciated by the audience.

The number of survey respondents, about one hundred the first day, shows that the Joystick audience is made up of many engaged concertgoers that readily share their thoughts and ideas with MSO. Many respondents give long and detailed accounts, which is often difficult to achieve through online surveys. It can be assumed, given the long answers and the time spent answering, that they believe that they are listened to and that they can influence the event. The respondents take for granted that the receiver of their answers, MSO, has a broad and deep knowledge of the gaming culture, as their answers reference particular gaming knowledge that demands considerable knowledge of the domain. MSO are seen as credible and knowledgeable and part of the audience is willing to become involved in a mutual learning process.

Concert formats that the Joystick respondents are particularly interested in are crossover formats where some want 'rock with strings', but many are also interested in more experimental formats where various genres meet on equal terms. These formats could possibly open up for a more mixed-gender audience. Furthermore, given that many of the respondents have attended other concert

formats and showed interest in learning more about classical music, the basis for developing new 'crossover formats' through mutual learning processes are good.

The audience shows considerable interest in social activities tied to the concert and many had a need to linger in the concert hall, to share and digest the experience. Social activities prior to the concert are also highly appreciated. 40 percent of the survey respondents socialized with friends or close others before the concert. To a large extent such activities should be left up to the audience to arrange on their own. However, MSO could favorably provide and arrange social activities prior to the concert to a larger extent than today.

The Joystick production, as such, showed that long-term mutual learning can lead to new ways of planning and communicating a concert. This form of working has allowed the partners to develop the concert simultaneously from within and outside the institution. It shows that when mutual trust and commitment is achieved, both the institution and the audience gain a deeper understanding of each other and they both become more committed, which in turn leads to the creation of a holistic meaningful experience. When it comes to the music, the audience has full respect for MSO's and the producers' competence and do not expect or even want to influence that to a large degree. However, given the opportunity, they enjoy being given the opportunity to influence part of the repertoire and they have many ideas of how Joystick could be developed, as well as suggestions on new concert formats. A central issue during the Joystick production was how the weaving of face-to-face and mediated communication could be done. There is no universal answer to how this weaving should be done. It demands a situated pluralistic view on aesthetic and communicative qualities and relationship building.